

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION IN THE EFFECT OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT (A Study on the Staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple)

Putu Bayu Dea Laksana¹, I Gusti Ayu Manuati Dewi²

¹ Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University; e-mail: laksanab954@gmail.com

² Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University

* Corresponding Author: Putu Bayu Dea Laksana

Abstract: This study aims to analyze the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was applied, involving 91 respondents. Data collection was conducted through surveys and interviews. The data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method. The results indicate that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, job satisfaction positively and significantly affects organizational commitment, and job satisfaction is proven to partially and complementarily mediate the effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

The global tourism sector continues to grow rapidly, with the World Travel and Tourism Council (2024) reporting a contribution of 10.4% to global GDP and the creation of more than 330 million jobs. In Indonesia, tourism serves as a key pillar of the national economy, with international tourist arrivals reaching 11.7 million in 2023, an increase of 22.5% from the previous year (BPS, 2024). This includes the Uluwatu Temple Tourism Area, which recorded 1.8 million visitors throughout 2024. This growth is inseparable from the role of human resources as a key element in operational performance, as organizational commitment is associated with loyalty, productivity, and low turnover rates (Anggreni & Budiani, 2021). However, increasing job demands pose challenges for staff in maintaining a balance between work and personal life, potentially affecting job satisfaction and commitment to the organization. A healthy work-life balance is believed to improve quality of life, job satisfaction, and employee commitment, as documented in previous studies (Badrianto & Ekhsan, 2021; Helmy & Pratama, 2021; Haeruddin et al., 2022; Septiani & Rama Chandra Jaya, 2024), although other studies such as Handayani et al. (2022) found that work-life balance does not directly influence organizational commitment.

The role of job satisfaction in mediating the effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment has been empirically confirmed by several studies (Bagus et al., 2023; Rampi et al., 2024), which concluded that work-life balance significantly affects organizational commitment through job satisfaction. Although many studies have explored the relationship between these variables, most focused on the hospitality and public service sectors, with limited research conducted in cultural tourist attraction management contexts such as the Uluwatu Temple area. As emphasized by Kinczel et al. (2025), local cultural factors must be considered in understanding

the dynamics of work-life balance, as perceptions of work and organizational loyalty are strongly influenced by cultural values. For this reason, the present study was conducted among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple.

The Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple is responsible for managing the Uluwatu Temple tourist attraction, located in Pecatu Village, Badung Regency, Bali, one of the most well-known tourist destinations in Indonesia. The attraction features a magnificent cliff-top temple with unique architectural carvings, surrounded by lush forests inhabited by monkeys, and complemented by the famous Kecak dance performance at sunset. Such an iconic and exotic setting attracts thousands of visitors every year.

A pre-survey conducted with five staff members representing roles in ticketing, marketing, accounting, restroom sanitation, and monkey handling generated responses summarized in Table 1. The results indicate that staff organizational commitment remains relatively low across affective, continuance, and normative dimensions.

Table 1. Pre-survey Data

No	Organizational Commitment Variables	Interview Answer Summary
1	Affective Commitment	The majority of respondents expressed pride in their work at the institution, which is under the auspices of the customary law, but many experienced burnout due to routine work, high workloads during peak tourist periods, and a lack of variety. Staff generally did not feel a strong emotional attachment to the organization, although some felt a sense of attachment that was more influenced by their social and cultural background than by a close relationship with the organization.
2	Ongoing Commitment	All respondents had, and often considered, leaving their jobs, but remained sluggish due to external factors such as economic necessity, convenient distance from home, lack of alternative employment options, and family responsibilities. The main disadvantages cited were the loss of a steady income and established social networks. However, almost all respondents did not perceive any loss in terms of career or personal development.
3	Normative Commitment	Moral responsibility was mentioned by some respondents, but it was generally not the primary reason for their persistence. This responsibility was based more on being a villager or a traditional citizen, rather than being part of a modern organizational system. Some respondents even stated they

didn't feel a significant moral obligation and would choose to leave if a better opportunity arose.

Source: Interview Results, Processed Data, 2025

The respondents stated that although they felt pride related to cultural and community roles, this sentiment was insufficient to generate strong loyalty or emotional attachment to the institution. Factors such as monotony, lack of career development, heavy workloads, and weak internal communication were identified as contributors to low commitment. This suggests that affective, normative, and continuance commitment have not developed optimally. Most staff remain motivated by economic, social, and geographical convenience rather than genuine attachment to the organization, indicating that organizational commitment is a critical issue requiring attention.

Based on the identified problems and pre-survey results, job satisfaction is used as a mediating variable to assess the influence of work-life balance on organizational commitment, as interviews revealed that staff tend to feel dissatisfied with their work when their emotional state at home is disrupted, affecting work performance and resulting in decreased job satisfaction. Therefore, this study is titled: *“The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Effect of Work-Life Balance on Organizational Commitment (A Study on the Staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple).”*

METHOD

This research employs a quantitative approach with a causal associative design to examine the relationship and influence among Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. The study site was selected in Pecatu Village due to the presence of organizational commitment-related concerns. The research variables consist of Work-Life Balance as the exogenous variable, Job Satisfaction as the mediating variable, and Organizational Commitment as the endogenous variable. All variables were operationalized based on relevant theories (Nahita & Saragih, 2021; Maimunah et al., 2024; Tama & Putra, 2022).

The study population consisted of 92 staff members, and the sample comprised 91 respondents holding positions below managerial level, selected via purposive sampling because they interact most frequently with the tourism work environment. Data were collected using a Likert scale questionnaire and supporting interviews. The research instrument met validity and reliability requirements, as demonstrated by Pearson Correlation values above 0.30 and Cronbach's Alpha scores above 0.60 for all variables, indicating suitability for further analysis (Sugiyono, 2021; Sekaran & Bougie, 2020).

Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS), which is appropriate for relatively small samples and models involving mediation. Analysis included evaluation of the outer model (convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability) and the inner model (R-square, path coefficient, effect size, and predictive relevance), including assessments of direct and indirect effects among variables. Hypothesis testing was conducted through t-statistics and p-values to determine relationships between constructs. This method

enables evaluation of how Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction contribute to improving Organizational Commitment among staff (Hair et al., 2021; Ghozali & Latan, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of the Uluwatu Temple Outer Area Tourism Object Management Agency

A brief History

The Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple is an official institution based on the traditional village (desa adat), established by the community of Desa Adat Pecatu in the late 1980s as a response to the increasing number of tourist visits since the 1970s, when the beauty of the Uluwatu cliffs and the sacredness of Pura Luhur Uluwatu became widely recognized. Along with tourism development, in the 1990s an entrance ticket system was introduced, basic facilities were arranged, and the Kecak Dance performance was presented as a main attraction. From the 2000s to the 2010s, management was strengthened through facility modernization, digitalization of services, implementation of the Tri Hita Karana philosophy, and utilization of revenue for village development, cultural preservation, and organizational strengthening.

Based on Traditional Village Decree No. 03/Kep-KDA/VI/2014, this institution has an organizational structure consisting of two divisions: a general division, which oversees security and cleanliness, and a retribution division, which manages the ticketing system and tourism services. In addition, the agency also manages the Padang-Padang Beach tourist destination, as well as the food court area and Uluwatu souvenir center. With a vision to become a professional, sustainable, and globally competitive tourism management institution based on desa adat, the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple implements its mission through professional management, cultural preservation, separation of sacred and tourism areas, transparent governance, application of sustainable tourism principles, and enhancement of competitiveness through digital innovation and human resource development.

Respondent Characteristics

Respondent characteristic data were collected to identify the profile of the research respondents. Based on the results of the study conducted on 91 staff members of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple, respondent characteristics include age, gender, and education, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Classification	Total (people)	Percentage
1	Age	20-30 Years	18	19.8
		31-40 Years	47	51.6
		>40 Years	26	28.6
		Total	91	100
2	Gender	Man	59	64.8
		Woman	32	35.2
		Total	91	100
3	Education	High School/Vocational School	43	47.3

Diploma	19	20.9
Bachelor	29	31.9
Total	91	100

Source: data processed in 2025

Based on Table 2, the number of respondents in this study was 91 staff of the Uluwatu Temple Outer Area Tourism Object Management Agency, with the age category dominated by the 31–40 year old group of 47 people or 51.6 percent, which indicates that the majority of staff are in the productive age group with a balance between physical ability and work experience. The composition based on gender shows a male dominance of 59 people or 64.8 percent, which indicates that most operational tasks such as security, parking, and field activities are handled more by male personnel. Viewed from the last level of education, the majority of respondents had a high school/vocational high school education of 43 people or 47.3 percent, which indicates that most of the positions held do not require higher education, but rather emphasize practical skills and discipline in carrying out operational tasks.

Description of Research Variables

Descriptive analysis was used to describe the research variables—organizational commitment, work-life balance, and job satisfaction—based on employees’ perceptions through their responses to each indicator in the research instrument. The interval categories were calculated using the formula of the highest score minus the lowest score, divided by the number of classes, resulting in an interval of 0.80 as the basis for determining the measurement criteria.

Table 3. Variable Description Criteria

Average Score	Criteria		
	Organizational Commitment	Work Life Balance	Job satisfaction
1.00 - 1.80	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
1.81 - 2.60	Low	Low	Low
2.61 - 3.40	Enough	Enough	Enough
3.41 - 4.20	Tall	Tall	Tall
4.21 - 5.00	Very high	Very high	Very high

Source: Processed by the author

Descriptive Analysis Results

Based on the descriptive analysis, the organizational commitment variable obtained an overall mean score of 3.39, which falls into the “moderate” category. This indicates that staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple have a moderately good level of organizational commitment. The lowest mean score was found in the item “I feel emotionally attached to the company,” with a mean of 3.19, while the highest mean score was on the item “I feel proud to be part of the company,” with a mean of 3.63. This shows that pride in being part of the organization is stronger than emotional attachment.

Meanwhile, the work-life balance variable has an average score of 3.33, also categorized as “moderate,” indicating that employees experience a moderate level of balance between work and personal life. The lowest mean score was recorded for the item “Working hours are in accordance with the agreed contract” (3.08), suggesting a perceived discrepancy regarding working hours. The highest mean score was on the statement “I work productively when my personal life is pleasant” (3.74), confirming that positive personal conditions enhance work productivity.

Furthermore, the job satisfaction variable has an average score of 3.38, which falls into the “moderate” category, showing that employees perceive a moderate level of job satisfaction. The lowest rating was found in the aspect of promotion opportunities (3.05), while the highest was in pride regarding their own work results (3.54).

Results of Inferential Analysis using the PLS (Partial Least Square) Method

The steps in analyzing data using PLS include evaluating the underlying models used in this test, namely the outer model and the inner model. The results of the outer and inner model tests are as follows:

Outer Model Testing

Measurement model testing, or outer model testing, is a component of the SEM model that aims to identify the relationship between latent variables (constructs that cannot be measured directly) and indicators. The purpose of this analysis is to ensure that the indicators used truly reflect the construct. The outer model evaluation also includes:

- 1) Convergent Validity Test

Table 4. Test results Outer Loadings

Statement<-Indicator	Outer Loadings	Information
Y1.1<- Organizational commitment	0.938	Valid
Y1.2<- Organizational commitment	0.885	Valid
Y1.3<- Organizational commitment	0.852	Valid
Y2.1<- Organizational commitment	0.929	Valid
Y2.2<- Organizational commitment	0.938	Valid
Y2.3<- Organizational commitment	0.922	Valid
Y3.1<- Organizational commitment	0.917	Valid
Y3.2<- Organizational commitment	0.853	Valid
Y3.3<- Organizational commitment	0.925	Valid
X1.1<- Work life balance	0.943	Valid
X1.2<- Work life balance	0.857	Valid

X2.1<- Work life balance	0.950	Valid
X2.2<- Work life balance	0.959	Valid
X3.1<- Work life balance	0.943	Valid
X3.2<- Work life balance	0.924	Valid
X4.1<- Work life balance	0.890	Valid
X4.2<- Work life balance	0.909	Valid
Z1.1<- Job satisfaction	0.885	Valid
Z1.2<- Job satisfaction	0.850	Valid
Z2.1<- Job satisfaction	0.816	Valid
Z2.2<- Job satisfaction	0.844	Valid
Z3.1<- Job satisfaction	0.769	Valid
Z3.2<- Job satisfaction	0.751	Valid
Z4.1<- Job satisfaction	0.785	Valid
Z4.2<- Job satisfaction	0.857	Valid
Z5.1<- Job satisfaction	0.812	Valid
Z5.2<- Job satisfaction	0.819	Valid

Source: data processed in 2025

Based on Table 4, the results of convergent validity can be seen in the organizational commitment variable where there are 9 items used to measure organizational commitment which have a greater outer loading value.

of 0.70, this means that all statements of organizational commitment are able to reflect organizational commitment. The evaluation results on the work-life balance variable where there are 8 items used to measure work-life balance have an outer loading value greater than 0.70, this means that all statements measuring work-life balance are able to reflect work-life balance. The evaluation results on the job satisfaction variable where there are 10 items used to measure job satisfaction have an outer loading value greater than 0.70, this means that all statements of job satisfaction are able to reflect job satisfaction.

2) Discriminant Validity Test

Table 5. Test Results Cross Loading

Item	Variables		
	Organizational commitment	Work-life balance	Job satisfaction
Y1.1	0.938	0.770	0.621
Y1.2	0.885	0.690	0.598
Y1.3	0.852	0.675	0.634
Y2.1	0.929	0.734	0.575
Y2.2	0.938	0.749	0.595
Y2.3	0.922	0.709	0.633
Y3.1	0.917	0.745	0.582
Y3.2	0.853	0.628	0.539
Y3.3	0.925	0.701	0.657
X1.1	0.737	0.943	0.604
X1.2	0.717	0.857	0.582
X2.1	0.753	0.950	0.579

X2.2	0.746	0.959	0.610
X3.1	0.727	0.943	0.594
X3.2	0.719	0.924	0.569
X4.1	0.695	0.890	0.533
X4.2	0.699	0.909	0.555
Z1.1	0.628	0.576	0.885
Z1.2	0.459	0.487	0.850
Z2.1	0.482	0.477	0.816
Z2.2	0.509	0.488	0.844
Z3.1	0.691	0.677	0.769
Z3.2	0.505	0.475	0.751
Z4.1	0.483	0.456	0.785
Z4.2	0.588	0.542	0.857
Z5.1	0.498	0.394	0.812
Z5.2	0.517	0.472	0.819

Source: data processed in 2025

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the correlation of the organizational commitment variable (Y) with the crossloadings value of 9 measuring items is higher than the correlation of job satisfaction (Z) and work-life balance (X). The correlation of the work-life balance variable (X) with the crossloadings value of 8 measuring items is higher than the correlation of job satisfaction (Z) and organizational commitment (Y). Then the correlation of the job satisfaction variable (Z) with the crossloadings value of 10 measuring items is higher than the correlation of the work-life balance indicator (X) and organizational commitment (Y). So it can be explained that all items in each variable are valid.

Other methods To assess discriminant validity, compare the average variance extracted for each variable with the correlation between the variable and other variables in the model. A model has sufficient discriminant validity if the AVE value is greater than 0.50. The results of the AVE test in the model can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Test Results Average Variance Extracted

Research Variables	Average Variance Eextracted (AVE)
Organizational commitment (Y)	0.823
Work-life balance(X)	0.851
Job satisfaction (Z)	0.672

Source: data processed in 2025

Based on Table 6, it can be explained that the AVE values of the variables organizational commitment, work life balance, job satisfaction are 0.823, 0.851 and 0.672, where each variable has an AVE value of each variable greater than 0.50, so the model can be said to be good.

3) Reliability Test

Table 7. Results of Reliability Testing and Cronbach's Alpha

Variables	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Organizational commitment (Y)	0.977	0.973	Reliable
Work-life balance(X)	0.979	0.975	Reliable

Job satisfaction (Z)	0.953	0.946	Reliable
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Source: data processed in 2025

Based on the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha test results in Table 10, the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values for the variables of organizational commitment, work-life balance, and job satisfaction are above 0.70. Therefore, the variables of organizational commitment, work-life balance, and job satisfaction have good reliability.

Inner Model Testing

Inner model testing is used to see the relationship between constructs. This evaluation covers several important aspects. The inner model testing can be seen as follows:

1) R-Square

Table 8. R-test resultssquare

Variables	R Square
Job satisfaction	0.394
Organizational commitment	0.666

Source: data processed in 2025

Based on Table 8 shows the R-square value of the job satisfaction variable of 0.394, this means that 39.4 percent of the variation in the construct of the job satisfaction variable can be explained by the work life balance variable, while the remaining 60.6 percent of the variation in the construct of the job satisfaction variable is explained by other variables outside the model. The R-square on the organizational commitment variable is 0.666, this means that 66.6 percent of the variation in the construct of the organizational commitment variable can be explained by the work life balance and job satisfaction variables, while the remaining 33.4 percent of the variation in the construct of the organizational commitment variable is explained by other variables outside the model.

2) Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q₂)

Q-Square predictive relevance(Q₂). Measures how well the observation values generated by the estimation model and its parameters. A Q-Square value > 0 indicates that the model has a predictive relevance value (Q₂). Conversely, if the Q-Square value < 0 indicates that the model does not have a predictive relevance value (Q₂). If the Q-Square value > 0.35 (categorized as a strong model), > 0.15 – 0.02 (moderate model) and < 0.02 (weak model). The calculation of Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q₂) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_2 &= 1 - (1 - R_1^2)(1 - R_2^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.394)(1 - 0.666) \\
 &= 1 - (0.606)(0.334) \\
 &= 1 - 0.202 = 0.798
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculation results Q₂ of 0.798 approaching 1. Referring to the criteria of the strength of the model based on the Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q₂) value, this model is classified as strong. The predictive-relevance value is 0.798, which means that 79.8 percent of the variation in the construct of the organizational commitment variable can be explained directly or indirectly by the work-life balance and job satisfaction variables in the research model, while the remaining 20.2 percent is explained by other variables outside the research model.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out in the Smart PLS 4.1 software analysis process using probability (p values). If p values are obtained < 0.05 (alpha 5%), or t statistic > 1.96 (t statistic > 1.96), then the test indicates that there is a significant influence between the latent variables, namely work-life balance, job satisfaction, organizational commitment. The results of the empirical model analysis of this research using the Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis tool produce the following results.

Picture Table 2 shows that there are four hypotheses in this study, where Hypothesis 1 states that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. Hypothesis 2 states that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. Hypothesis 3 states that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. Hypothesis 4 states that work-life balance has an effect on organizational commitment with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. The results of the research hypothesis testing are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Original Sample	t statistic	p values	Information
Direct Influence				
Work-life balance-> Organizational commitment	0.606	6,972	0,000	Significant
Work-life balance-> Job satisfaction	0.628	10,823	0,000	Significant
Job satisfaction -> Organizational commitment	0.286	3,369	0.001	Significant
Indirect Influence				
Work-life balance-> Job satisfaction -> Organizational commitment	0.179	3,508	0.001	Significant

Source: data processed in 2025

Table 9 shows the results of the PLS analysis used to test the hypotheses in this study. The hypothesis testing in this study can be described as follows:

1) The influence of work life balance on organizational commitment

Based on Table 9, the original sample value of the influence of work-life balance on organizational commitment is 0.606, with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a t-statistic of 6.972 > 1.96, indicating that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. This result means that if work-life balance increases, it will have a significant impact on increasing organizational commitment. Therefore, the first hypothesis in this study is accepted.

2) The influence of work life balance on job satisfaction

Based on Table 9, the original sample value of the influence of work-life balance on job satisfaction is 0.628, with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 and a t-statistic of 10.823 > 1.96, indicating that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. This result means that if work-life balance increases, it will have a significant impact on job satisfaction. Therefore, the second hypothesis in this study is accepted.

3) The influence of job satisfaction on organizational commitment

Based on the Table 9, it can be seen that the original sample value of the influence of job satisfaction on organizational commitment is 0.286, with p values of 0.001 < 0.05 and t statistics of 3.369 > 1.96 indicating that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This result means that if job satisfaction increases, it will have a significant impact on increasing organizational commitment. Therefore, the third hypothesis in this study is accepted.

4) The role of job satisfaction mediates the influence of work life balance on organizational commitment.

Based on Table 9, the results of the indirect effect analysis show the original sample value of 0.179 with p values of 0.001 < 0.05, and t statistics of 3.508 > 1.96, which means that the job satisfaction variable can mediate the influence between work-life balance and organizational commitment. Based on the testing of the role of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of work-life balance on organizational commitment, it can be seen that job satisfaction partially mediates the complementary influence of work-life balance on organizational commitment, this is because work-life balance has a significant positive direct influence on organizational commitment and work-life balance has a significant positive effect through job satisfaction on organizational commitment. So the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Discussion

The results of the study show that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on the organizational commitment of staff at the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple, thus supporting the first hypothesis. The better the balance between work and personal life perceived by staff, the higher their commitment to the organization, as reflected in their pride in being part of the institution and their willingness to participate in various organizational activities. These findings are consistent with Social Exchange Theory, which posits that when organizations provide support for employees' work-life balance, employees reciprocate with stronger commitment. This is also in line with previous empirical studies that have found a positive relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment.

Furthermore, the analysis shows that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, supporting the second hypothesis. Staff who can maintain a balance between their work and personal lives tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs, especially when personal conditions support work productivity. This job satisfaction is reflected in pride in work outcomes, perceptions of fairness in compensation, and positive working relationships. These findings are consistent with Social Exchange Theory and prior research that identifies work-life balance as an important determinant of job satisfaction.

In addition, job satisfaction has been shown to have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, supporting the third hypothesis and confirming that higher job satisfaction leads to higher organizational commitment. The mediation test results further show that job satisfaction plays a complementary partial mediating role in the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment, thereby supporting the fourth hypothesis. This means that good work-life balance not only directly enhances organizational commitment, but also indirectly strengthens it through increased job satisfaction.

Overall, these findings reinforce the principles of Social Exchange Theory, whereby organizational support for employees' life balance leads to positive responses in the form of satisfaction and commitment. The results are also consistent with various previous empirical studies that emphasize the strategic role of work-life balance and job satisfaction in building sustainable organizational commitment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. This means that the work-life balance perceived by staff contributes to increasing their organizational commitment.
2. Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. This indicates that better work-life balance leads to higher levels of job satisfaction.
3. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. This implies that higher job satisfaction experienced by staff will enhance their organizational commitment.
4. Job satisfaction is able to partially and complementarily mediate the effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment among staff of the Tourism Management Agency of the Outer Area of Uluwatu Temple. This means that employees who experience a good work-life balance tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs, which in turn will increase their organizational commitment.

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